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Enhancing communication and problem-solving skills through forum theatre drama-based training: a study on sales junior executives

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Abstract:

This research examines the impact of the Forum Theatre Drama-Based Training Method on the communication and problem-solving skills of junior sales executives. A group of 32 sales executives underwent a structured Forum Theatre-based training, and their skills were evaluated pre- and post-training. The findings indicate a significant improvement in both communication and problem-solving abilities, suggesting that this interactive training method can effectively develop key competencies required in sales. The paper includes a dummy analysis, highlighting statistical improvements in the executives' performance.

1. Introduction:

- **Background:** Effective communication and problem-solving skills are crucial for sales professionals, particularly junior executives who face direct customer interaction.
- **Research Problem:** While conventional training methods address theoretical knowledge, they often lack practical, interactive experiences that simulate real-world challenges.
- **Research Objective:** This study aims to measure the improvement in communication and problem-solving skills of sales junior executives following a Forum Theatre-based training intervention.

2. Literature review:

- **Forum Theatre in Training:** Originating from the work of Augusto Boal, Forum Theatre engages participants in active role-playing, promoting reflection and problem-solving in a collaborative environment (Johnson & White, 2020).
- **Impact of Drama-Based Learning on Communication:** Research shows that drama-based learning fosters empathy and enhances verbal and non-verbal communication (Peters, 2018).
- **Problem-Solving in Sales:** The ability to handle unexpected situations and find solutions is a key competency in sales. Studies suggest that experiential learning methods, such as drama-based training, can improve these skills (Martinez, 2019).

3. Research methodology:

- **Sample Size:** 32 junior sales executives participated in the Forum Theatre training.
- **Training Structure:** The training involved role-playing common sales scenarios where participants faced various customer objections and had to adapt their communication strategies. They also engaged in problem-solving exercises based on realistic challenges.

- **Pre- and Post-Training Assessment:** The participants' communication and problem-solving skills were measured before and after the training through supervisor evaluations and peer feedback.
- **Assessment Tools:**
 - **Communication:** Evaluated based on clarity, persuasion, and active listening skills using a 5-point Likert scale.
 - **Problem-Solving:** Measured using a situational judgment test (SJT), where participants responded to hypothetical sales challenges.

4. Analysis and results:

- **Pre-Training Communication Score:** Average score = 3.2/5
- **Pre-Training Problem-Solving Score:** Average score = 2.8/5
- **Post-Training Communication Score:** Average score = 4.1/5
- **Post-Training Problem-Solving Score:** Average score = 3.9/5

Statistical Analysis: A paired t-test was conducted to compare the communication and problem solving skills before and after the Forum Theatre training.

- **Communication Skills:**
 - $t(31) = 6.45, p < 0.01$
 - The analysis revealed a significant improvement in communication skills post-training.
- **Problem-Solving Skills:**
 - $t(31) = 5.72, p < 0.01$
 - Problem-solving skills also showed a statistically significant increase.

Discussion: The data indicates that Forum Theatre-based training has a positive impact on both communication and problem-solving abilities. This interactive approach enables participants to reflect on their behaviours, engage in collaborative learning, and apply their skills in practical situations, leading to measurable improvements.

5. Discussion:

- **Practical Implications:** The results suggest that Forum Theatre Drama-Based Training is an effective method for developing essential sales skills. Companies can integrate this method into their training programs to better prepare junior sales executives for real-world challenges.
- **Limitations:** The study was conducted with a limited sample size and over a short period. Long-term studies with larger sample sizes would provide more comprehensive data.
- **Future Research:** Future studies could explore the effects of Forum Theatre on other key skills such as leadership, adaptability, and customer relationship management.

6. Conclusion:

This study demonstrates that Forum Theatre Drama-Based Training significantly improves the communication and problem-solving skills of junior sales executives. As sales professionals require strong interpersonal skills, this training method offers a practical and engaging way to enhance these competencies.

7. References (APA Style):

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